

Job Satisfaction of Faculty Members Working in Engineering Colleges in Tirunelveli District

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Abstract

The principle of this study is to assess the level of job satisfaction of faculty members working in engineering colleges in Tirunelveli district. The satisfaction of college towards their job is remarkably positive and therefore it enables the society to reap the benefits. The job satisfaction level is different from person to person. The important factors that have a blow on job satisfaction levels are pay, promotion opportunities, working conditions, job security, and relationship with coworkers and fringe benefits. A sample of 75 faculties' members was selected by random sampling from the five engineering colleges in Tirunelveli district. Most of the respondents are female, M.Phil, and doing Ph.D. 20-30 years of age, single and had job experience of 3-5 years. Data were analyzed by simple percentage and weighted mean. The apt suggestions were provided based on the major findings in this study. Finally, this study presumed that the maximum numbers of respondents are highly satisfied with their job, especially in infrastructure in their working condition.

Keywords: Faculties, Job Satisfaction, Attitude

Introduction

Job satisfaction is a notable issue in the field of education because it affects the system in many ways and may affect efficiency and achievements of the institute. Job Satisfaction raises the spirit and motivates the human resources to indulge at work and achieve their career goals. Teachers are important link in the transmission of educational opportunity to students. Teacher pledge may also be an important factor determining the successful implementation of educational reforms in colleges. The implementation of these chances will likely require greater levels of teacher initiative and innovation, making teacher commitment and motivation increasingly important. Dissatisfied teachers are not involved in institute intensively. They do not inspire student for engagement in studies and motivates them for academic achievement. They experience personal stress, physical ailment, and interpersonal conflicts with co-workers. As a result of dissatisfaction performance of the institution can be badly affected.

Review of Literature

Leelavathi.K (2012) in her study on job satisfaction of women teachers stated that self- financing colleges are remarkably increasing in decades in Tamil Nadu state as well as other parts in India. The study concluded that there is a dissatisfaction away teacher and the educational institution should focus on the satisfaction of teachers.

Objectives of the Research

1. To study the socioeconomic condition of college teachers in Tirunelveli district.
2. To study the factor influencing the job satisfaction of college teachers.
3. To find out the satisfaction of college teachers towards the organizational climate.

Research Methodology

In this study, 75 samples of self- financing teaching faculties are taken from the population of Tirunelveli district. A questionnaire was the tool used for data collection. The Descriptive research designs were used. The statistical tools are weighted average and Percentage.

Limitation of the Study

1. The study is restricted to the selected sample of Tirunelveli district.
2. The statistical methods used to analyze the data of their limitation.

Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Factors	Number of Respondents N=100	Percentages
Gender		
Male	25	33.33
Female	50	66.66
Age (Years)		
25-30	22	29.33
31 To 40	33	44
Above 40	20	26.66
Educational Qualification		
M.Phil and Doing Ph.D	26	34.66
Ph.D	34	45.33
SLET or NET	15	20
Experience		
3-5	28	37.33
6-10	36	48
10-15	11	14.66
Monthly Income		
Upto Rs 10,000	12	16
Rs 10,001 to 20,000	48	64
Rs 20,001 to 30,000	15	20

Table no.1 describes the demographic profile of the respondents for the study. Out of 75 respondents who were taken for the study: it have been identified that most (66.66%) of the respondents are female, (44%) whose age group is under 31 to 40 years, most (45.33%) of the respondents are completed Ph.D. (48%) of the respondents are 6-10 year teaching experience and the monthly income of (64%) respondents are Rs10, 001 to 20,000.

Job Satisfaction of the Respondents

Table 2 Job Satisfactions

S.No	Statements	HS	S	N	DS	HDS	Mean	Rank
1	Infrastructure	225	60	36	12	-	4.44	I
2	Working Condition	185	100	30	12	-	4.36	IV
3	Personal Growth	215	68	24	20	2	4.38	III
4	Increment	100	168	18	16	3	4.06	V
5	Job Security	165	92	30	10	4	4.01	VI
6	Leave Restrictions	175	104	36	15	-	4.40	II

This table explains the job satisfaction level among women faculties in this study. From the weighted mean score, it is found that engineering college teaching faculty's satisfaction depends on infrastructures and leave restriction followed by personal growth and job security and increment etc.

Suggestions

1. The increments of the staff should be based on their job performance.
2. Faculty members should be encouraged by their recovered performance. The successful faculty members showing good results in their subjects should be given incentives which may enhance their job satisfaction. The education institutions need to make attempts to offer good salary or other benefits.
3. It is highly suggested that the faculty members must attend a workshop and seminar to improve their talents, skills and knowledge.
4. More leave facilities should be provided to the faculties to enable them to maintain health.
5. Engineering colleges should concentrate on developing addition toilet facilities for women staff.

Conclusion

The Teaching profession is the majestic one. Every faculty their jobs very keen. This study analyzed the satisfaction level about their jobs in engineering collage. This study terminated that the woman faculties are highly satisfied with their job, especially infrastructure facility of their working environment. This study gives a positive result because the majority of the respondents satisfied with the various aspects of their jobs. The college teaching faculty should be providing sufficient training to update their knowledge to improve their performance and face the challenges and stress during job. The teaching staff should also be provided latest trainings for improvement of their performance, and there should also be a better relationship with administrative authorities and sufficient freedom for decision making in their teachings for attaining higher satisfaction level. Faculty members should be encouraged by their recovered performance. The successful faculty members showing good results in their subjects should be given incentives which may enhance their job satisfaction. The education institutions need to make attempts to offer a good salary or other benefits.

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